

PROCRASTINATION AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS: A GENDER BASED STUDY

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Abstract

The objective of present study was to explore the procrastination among male and female secondary school teachers. The findings of the study revealed that 29.33% female teachers have low, 49.33% average and 21.33% female secondary school teachers have high level of procrastination. Similarly 23.33% male secondary school teachers have low, 49.33% average and 27.33% secondary school teachers have high level of procrastination. Findings of the study revealed that no significance difference have been found between the scores of procrastination of male and female secondary school teachers.

Keywords: *Procrastination, Low procrastination, Average procrastination, High procrastination, Male Secondary School Teachers, Female Secondary School Teachers*

Introduction:

Procrastination is the tendency to delay tasks until an individual experiences discomfort. The most commonly used definition of procrastination is, the act of needlessly delaying tasks to the point of subjective discomfort (Solomon & Rothblum 1984). Klein (1971) in keeping with the term's Latin origins of 'pro meaning forward forth or in favors of,' and crastinus' meaning "of tomorrow". People with high procrastination may suffer lot, one can lose the job, family life may suffer, students may be low achievers etc. Due to all these hurtful effects, one should be careful about this tendency. It is rightly said that procrastination is the thief of time because we delay a task as much as possible. To some extent we all procrastinate, at home or at workplace. Procrastination is a common human weakness; there are numerous books on the topic, mostly written from time management and self-help perspectives. The topic is studied under numerous disciplines and has been framed as an aspect of behavioral economics, personality, motivation, self-regulation, and neuropsychology. Procrastination has been shown to negatively affect various life domains, including those related to academics, health, finances, and the workplace. If anyone habitually turn in projects late or dawdle until the last

minute, the people who depend on him/her such as friends, family, co-workers, and fellow students can become resentful. Not surprisingly, then, many ideas for overcoming procrastination have been accumulating, some of which have been formulated in well-conceptualized interventions programs and books. Researchers study procrastination as self-regulation failure (Morford, 2008). Procrastination can be divided in further five subtitles-general procrastination, academic procrastination, decision-making procrastination, neurotic procrastination, nonfunctional procrastination. It has been seen that procrastination includes such behavior that affect the productivity of individual in a negative way. Balkis & Duru (2009) conducted a study on pre-service teachers to study academic procrastination behavior. They were focusing on association between individual preferences and demographics. The results show that 23% of total sample exhibited a high level of procrastination behavior. Findings showed that procrastination was significantly differed by gender, time preference for studying courses and exams. It was seen that academic achievement negatively related to academic procrastination behavior. Balkis, et al. (2013) revealed that rational academic beliefs have a direct impact on academic procrastination and time preferences to study for exams. Academic rational beliefs also effect academic achievement indirectly by mediation of academic procrastination and time preferences to study for exams. It was also seen that academic procrastination has a direct impact on academic achievement and it is also affected by arbitration of time preferences to study for exams. This study examined an association between academic beliefs and academic procrastination. Michinov, et al. (2011) conducted a study to explore the influence of procrastination on online learning through the participation of the participants. The relationship found between the performance of learners and procrastination was negative. The high procrastinators less participated in discussions and they were less successful, on the other hand low procrastinators showed good performance. For teaching online activities and to motivating participation, the investigators have suggested some practical implications. Christopher (1998) presented a research note on causes and consequences of academic procrastination. The study examines whether students who are intrinsically motivated about learning procrastinate less than those students who are externally motivated and also explore the consequences of procrastination. It indicates that students whose motivation is external are more likely to procrastinate while procrastination is associated with poor academic performance and negative student attitudes. Ugurlu (2013) conducted a study on principles and vice-principles showed that rational decision making styles and procrastination tendencies do not significantly differ with respect to the age. There is minor but significant correlation between different decision making styles and

procrastination behavior of school administrators. It was concluded that experienced principles could result in better performance against procrastination. Beside it, a healthy surrounding and positive school climate, along with rational decision are necessary for effective management procedure in schools. Uzun et. Al.(2014) revealed that internet addiction was existing among pre-service ICT teachers and there was significant relationship among variables. It was also found that general procrastination is a better predictor than academic procrastination to predict internet addiction. Falak & Nadia (2014) conducted a study to examine significant relationship among procrastination, delay of gratification and job satisfaction with work related stress as an intervening variable among high school teachers. Negative correlation was found between procrastination and job satisfaction but a positive correlation between delay of gratification and job satisfaction. It was concluded that when teachers are not procrastinating on their jobs and score high on delay of gratification they will be more satisfied with their jobs and feel less stressed.

Objectives:

1. To study the level of procrastination among male and female secondary school teachers.
2. To study the difference in procrastination between male and female secondary school teachers.

Hypothesis:

No significance difference exists in procrastination between male and female secondary school teachers.

Methodology

The investigator used descriptive method to conduct the present research. A sample of 300 secondary school teachers was selected for the study from Ludhiana district of Punjab. The male-female ratio was 50:50. For collecting the required information from the subjects the investigators used self developed Procrastination Scale. Mean, Percentage, Standard Deviation, Quartile, and t-test were used to analyze the data.

Results

Procrastination among male and female secondary school teachers have been studied under following headings:

1. Level of Procrastination between Male and Female Secondary School Teachers

In order to explore the level of procrastination between male and female secondary school teachers, the investigator used self constructed procrastination scale for collecting information from secondary school teachers. The scores of the procrastination scale were

calculated and divided into three groups i.e. low procrastination group (LPG), average procrastination group (APG), and high procrastination group (HPG) as per the norms of the scale. The subjects having less than 149 scores belong to LPG while subjects having scores between 149-190 falls in APG and the subjects having more than 190 scores belong to HPG. The results pertaining to different levels of procrastination of male and female secondary school teachers have been presented in table 1.

Table 1

Level of procrastination among male and female secondary school teachers

Level of Procrastination	FSST		MSST	
	N (150)	Percentage	N (150)	Percentage
LPG	44	29.33%	35	23.33%
APG	74	49.33%	74	49.33%
HPG	32	21.33%	41	27.33%

The results of the above table revealed that 29.33% female teachers have low procrastination level, 49.33% female teachers have average procrastination level and 21.33% female secondary school teachers have high procrastination level.

Similarly 23.33% male secondary school teachers have low procrastination level, 49.33% male secondary school teachers have average procrastination level and 27.33% secondary school teachers have high procrastination level.

2. Difference in Procrastination between Male and Female Secondary School Teachers

In order to find out the difference in procrastination between male and female secondary school teachers, the investigator used procrastination scale for collecting information from 150 male secondary school teachers (MSST) and 150 female secondary school teachers (FSST). Thereafter the scores of the male and female secondary school teachers were tabulated and t-test was applied. The results have been presented in the table 2.

Table 2

Difference between Male and Female Secondary School Teachers in Procrastination

Group	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Result
FSST	150	166.32	34.245	1.697	Insignificant
MSST	150	172.58	29.458		

The table 2 revealed the mean difference in procrastination scores of male and female secondary school teachers. The mean of procrastination scores of female secondary school

teachers were 166.32 and of male secondary school teachers were 172.58. The standard deviation of procrastination scores of female teachers was 34.245 and of male teachers were 29.458 respectively. The t-value found to be 1.697 which was found insignificant at 0.05 level of confidence. This means that there was no significance difference in the scores of procrastination of male and female secondary school teachers. The hypothesis of the study which stated that “There exists no significant difference in procrastination between male and female secondary school teachers” was accepted, because there was no statistically significant difference in the procrastination scores of male and female secondary school teachers. This may be due to the nature of variable (procrastination) which is equally distributed in both the gender. It can be found in every person without any difference based on gender. To the best knowledge of the investigator no study has been conducted which can support the present findings.

Conclusions

- 29.33% female teachers have low procrastination level, 49.33% female teachers have average procrastination level and 21.33% female secondary school teachers have high procrastination level.
- 23.33% male secondary school teachers have low procrastination level, 49.33% male secondary school teachers have average procrastination level and 27.33% secondary school teachers have high procrastination level.
- The t-value between the scores of procrastination of male and female secondary school teachers found to be 1.697 which was insignificant at 0.05 level of confidence. This means that there was no significance difference in the scores of procrastination of male and female secondary school teachers.

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